

Practical: Network Meta-Analysis Using R Package netmeta

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R packages

We use R functions from R package **netmeta** in this practical which is an add-on package to **meta**.

```
library("netmeta")
settings.meta(digits = 2, digits.se = 3)
```

Parkinson dataset

We utilize the Parkinson dataset from R package **netmeta**. However, first, we have a look at the list of datasets in **netmeta** (the description of datasets typically starts with “*Network meta-analysis ...*”).

```
help(package = "netmeta")
```

You can get more information about the Parkinson dataset by reading the help page.

```
help(Franchini2012)
```

Network meta-analysis of treatments for Parkinson's disease

Description:

Network meta-analysis comparing the effects of a number of treatments for Parkinson's disease.

The data are the mean lost work-time reduction in patients given dopamine agonists as adjunct therapy in Parkinson's disease (Franchini et al. 2012). The data are given as sample size, mean and standard deviation in each trial arm. Treatments are placebo and four active drugs. These data are used as an example in the supplemental material of Dias et al. (2013) where placebo is coded as 1 and the four active drugs as 2 to 5.

Load the Parkinson data and look at the format of the data.

```
data(Franchini2012)
head(Franchini2012, 2)
```

```
View(Franchini2012)
```

Transform data set

Transform data from wide arm-based format to contrast-based format.

```
p3 <- pairwise(list(Treatment1, Treatment2, Treatment3),
  n = list(n1, n2, n3), mean = list(y1, y2, y3), sd = list(sd1, sd2, sd3),
```

```
data = Franchini2012, studlab = Study)
head(p3, 2)
```

R function *metacont* is called internally for a continuous outcome (see help page of *metacont* for more details). Which effect measure is utilized in the analysis?

```
gs("smcont")
```

Network meta-analysis

Next, conduct a random effects network meta-analysis with placebo as reference treatment using the R object created with *pairwise*.

```
net6 <- netmeta(p3, common = FALSE, ref = "plac")
net6
```

How many treatments and trials are included? (see printout of net6)

How many of them are multi-arm trials?

```
table(net6$narms)
```

How many and which designs occur?

```
net6$designs # list of designs
```

How many and which direct pairwise comparisons are given?

```
with(net6, table(paste0(treat1, sep.trts, treat2)))
net6$A.matrix
```

Network graph

Draw the network using a circular layout. By default, line width is proportional to the number of studies providing direct comparisons.

```
netgraph(net6, points = TRUE, cex.points = 4, cex = 1.5,
number.of.studies = TRUE)
```

Now, use the argument 'iterate = TRUE'.

```
netgraph(net6, points = TRUE, cex.points = 4, cex = 1.5,
number.of.studies = TRUE, iterate = TRUE)
```

Optional: You can create 3-D plots using the **rgl** library.

```
# install.packages("rgl")
# netgraph(net6, dim = "3d", col = 1)
```

Forest plots

Produce a forest plot with the default settings.

```
forest(net6)
```

The variable 'k' stored in net6 contains the number of direct comparisons. We can plot them in the forest plot and sort by decreasing treatment effect.

```
forest(net6, sortvar = TE,  
  leftcols = c("studlab", "k"),  
  leftlabs = c("Drug", "Direct\nstudies"),  
  xlab = "Response to treatment")
```

Now, generate a forest plot with pramipexole, i.e., the most effective treatment, as reference treatment.

```
forest(net6, ref = "pram",  
  label.left = "Favours other treatment",  
  label.right = "Favours Pramipexole")
```

Finally, generate a forest plot of pramipexole compared to other treatments as reference.

```
forest(net6, ref = "pram", baseline = FALSE,  
  label.left = "Favours Pramipexole",  
  label.right = "Favours other treatment")
```